

Attaining School Improvement through Internal and External Stakeholders Participation

Yveth L. Castro

Faculty, Department of Education, Cebu, Philippines

ABSTRACT

It is not deniable that stakeholders play an important role in managing educational institution. They are the partners of the school leaders in making the schools conducive to teaching and learning. Further, they are also responsible for attaining the learning outcomes through their active participation. This study assessed the level of implementation of internal and external stakeholders' participation on school-based management. Based from the results of the study, the researcher concluded that the level of participation of internal and external stakeholders in school based management program was still in the process of adjustments. In addition, principal and the teachers were bombarded with additional task and this affected their limited time at school and teaching duties. Moreover, lack of financial resources was also the problem on the implementation. Hence, the researcher believed that there are more things to improve before we can attain the mission of this program. This research study might be deliberated by the public officials, school heads, teachers, parents and different stakeholders so that they will be encouraged to continuously support the schools operation for the benefit of all the stakeholders.

KEYWORDS: *Internal and Stakeholders Participation, School Based Management, Descriptive Methods in Research*

INTRODUCTION

Throughout the past 20 to 30 years there was a primary shift towards more self-control and self-governance in instructional institutions during the world. This fashion is clear in some of the countries such as America, Australia, Canada, New Zealand, the United Kingdom, and jump international locations, like Singapore, Thailand and Hong Kong. Decentralization and devolution of authority to high school level have emerged as a phenomenon in most training structures around the globe. In this context, many researchers verify that one of the huge reforms in the cutting-edge restructuring of faculty systems has been the devolution of decision making authority to high school through a move towards college-based control (Stevenson et. al 2007).

Caldwell (2005) defines school-based manipulate as "the systematic decentralization to the college degree of authority and responsibility to make selections on large subjects related to high school operations inside a centrally decided framework of goals, regulations, curriculum, necessities, and accountability. In essence, college-based totally manipulate is based absolutely at the thoughts of shared-governance (De Guzman, 2007).

It recognizes that each unit inside the education paperwork has a specific role and challenge and obligation inherent inside the office. within the university context, decentralization, which paved the manner for faculty-based totally completely control practices, and manipulate trouble

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at huge. It is able to be wide or constrained depending on how college principals percent and distribute authority and the quantity to which they expect obligation and duty. Therefore, inputting SBM at an artwork, the gadget needs the university administrator who recognizes the manner to manipulate assets and colleges, who can assume strategically and who apprehend the way to help operation, subsidized via the valuable office this is lean and might offer a course, coverage, assets and requirements. School-based control in almost all of its manifestations involved internal and outside members in school selection-making. due to the fact, these contributors have an incentive to enhance children's training. As an end result, SBM can be expected to enhance pupil achievement and different consequences as these neighborhood human beings demand closer monitoring of faculty personnel, better student opinions, a closer match among the faculty's needs and its policies, and greater efficient use of sources (Kagia et. al, 2007).

Furthermore, over the past many years, scholars placed that SBM can empower schools on the way to make bigger a better pleasant educational method, greater healthful training/getting to know environments, and superior scholar results in factors out that SBM is typically concerned with a gadget of educational decentralization in order to provide a boost to and empower school companies. In short, the system can empower stakeholders within school groups, growth participation in selection-making, and provide possibilities to percentage power and authority at the college

stage through the forum of a faculty council or board. This has resulted in the interior the advent of more wholesome education/studying environments main to more green and effective faculties with exceptional schooling (Gamage, 2007).

Moreover, SBM has more and more grow to be an international motion in the direction of autonomy for shared-decision making and a partnership inside the faculty network for the functions of attaining college improvements (Brown, 2007).

However, studies in the last ten years have discovered a selection of barriers and challenges to the implementation of SBM. Many researchers document that the barriers include poor resources in colleges, lack of expert improvement on leadership for school leaders, confusion at the part of school councils on the subject of new roles and responsibilities, difficulties of coordination, lack of choice-making authority, lack of information, low parental participation, and underneath funding of education by way of governments (Chen, 2011).

Nonetheless, the impact of SBM on training first-class, such as pupil outcomes, remains a contentious issue, with some researchers arguing that SBM results in more suitable instructional outcomes even as others contend that SBM results in the deterioration of instructional exceptional particularly a few of the weakest faculties. The variety of SBM processes and the contexts in which they're implemented makes the debate approximately SBM great a complex one. The assessment of SBM is complicated by way of the range of approaches to and factors of decentralization that collectively represent 'SBM' and by way of the institutional and sociocultural contexts in which they are carried out. Though a few research in latest years have discovered that SBM reforms are related to stepped forward education effects and procedures (Gropello, 2006).

In the Philippines, SBM absolutely management emerges as officially implemented as a governance framework of DepEd with the passage of RA 9155 in 2001 as a criminal cover. The implementation of the Governance of the number one training In 2001 supplied the mandate for decentralizing the machine of college manage and diagnosed the function of the nearby government units and different stakeholders as partners in schooling provider transport. With the enactment of RA 9155, it's far hereby declared the coverage of the united states of America to shield and sell the right of all citizens to pleasant number one schooling and to make such schooling accessible to throughout supplying all Filipino kids a unfastened and obligatory training on the simple stage and free training on the immoderate faculty diploma that promotes high-quality schooling for all (Bautista, 2009).

The SBM programmed turned into designed to improve student results through two most important venues: with the aid of empowering the faculty network to perceive schooling priorities and to allocate the college upkeep and operating budgets to the one's priorities (consisting of curriculum-enrichment programs); and by means of enhancing transparency and duty thru the once a year implementation plans and school record playing cards. however, the SBM program articulated no express assumptions concerning the time-frame within which enhancements in scholar fulfillment have been anticipated to

take location. Systematic statistics on the level of uptake and implementation of the important thing features of the reforms are also not to be had (Khattari et.al, 2010).

It is clear that SBM could provide an alternative model for managing schools in order to achieve autonomy, participation, effectiveness, productivity, and accountability in the school. School-based management had been implemented in North City Central School for a long period of time already, however, no assessment so far had been conducted as to the effectiveness of the program. Hence, this study will be conducted.

Objective of the Study

This research will transcend the opportunities to understand whether internal and external stakeholders understand their roles as one of change makers. Hence, this research assessed the level of internal and external stakeholders' participation as dimensions in school-based management and issues and concerns relating to school based management.

Methodology

This study utilized descriptive research method of research. Using adaptive survey questionnaire, the data were analyzed using mean, percentage and t-test.

Results and Discussions

Internal Stakeholder

Internal stakeholders are the school heads, teachers, students and parents of students and their associations who directly work for the improvement of school performance. Their inputs about the school's strengths, weaknesses, threats and opportunities are necessary in the agenda for school improvement.

Figure1. School Head

Figure2. Teachers

Figure 1 presents the internal stakeholders' participation in school based management. Based on the results gathered, teachers are trained on curriculum content and pedagogy, got the highest weighted mean of 2.67, which verbally

described as well practiced. Overall the data for principal respondents got a weighted mean of 2.28 which verbally described as practiced. This entails that internal stakeholders participation as observed by the principal were functional as one of the stakeholders. This means that there is still a need to motivate them to get involved in the process in order to reach in well practiced. Though teachers were trained on the curriculum content and pedagogy, there is a need for them to participate on the overall improvement of school based management process. Teachers group on the other hand, item 4 also got the highest weighted mean of

1.86, which verbally described as practiced, while item 5 got the lowest weighted mean of 1.40 which verbally described as less practiced. Overall, the teacher’s group got an overall weighted mean of 1.63 which verbally described as less practice. This entails that teacher’s observation and as one of the internal stakeholders perceived that internal stakeholders were not fully participating on the overall outcome of school based management. This means that teachers perceived that internal stakeholders were given an understanding but not directed to what needs to be done by them.

External Stakeholders Participation

External stakeholders are composed of community members, people from non-governmental organization or NGOs, and the local government officials who have a stake in the education of the children. Their participation in the strategic planning for school Improvement and attainment of learning outcomes is crucial.

Figure3. School Head

Figure4 Teachers

Figure 3 and 4 presents the external stakeholders’ participation in school based management. Based on the data gathered, item 3 and 9 which refers to “external stakeholders demonstrate initiative, openness and build effective relationships to contribute to the attainment of the organization’s visions, mission and goals”, and “external stake holders participate in setting of learning targets”, got the highest weighted mean of 2.50, which verbally described as well practiced, while item 1 and 5 refers to “external stakeholders are organized and made aware of their rights and responsibilities as education stakeholders” and external stakeholders understand their respective roles and responsibilities on SBM” got the lowest weighted mean of 2.14 which verbally described as practice. Overall the data for principal respondents got a weighted mean of 2.33 which verbally described as practiced. This entails that the participation of external stakeholders as perceived by the principals were functional but need to encourage to fully participate on the overall outcome of the program. This means that external stakeholders should be guided and empowered to participate actively in the implementation of the program.

Teachers group on the other hand, item 9 got the highest weighted mean of 1.96 refers to “External stakeholders participate in setting of learning targets”, which verbally described as practiced. While item 5 refers to “External stakeholders understand their respective roles and responsibilities on SBM; and are organized for participation in SBM processes” got a lowest weighted mean of which verbally described as less practice. Overall, as perceived by the teacher group in terms of external stakeholder participation got an overall weighted mean of 1.75, which verbally described as practice. This implies that teachers perceived that external stakeholders have known their responsibilities, however, might not have been tapped to fully engage on the process and development of the program. Arachi (2015) stated on the results of his study thatthe principals and the internal community members of schools are not willing to welcome ideas, suggestions and criticisms made by the external community members. Therefore, the decision making process is not functioning in a democratic manner. This study also revealed that the participation of stakeholders in school management is not encouraged by the school leaders. Hence, there must be a good relationship between the internal and external stakeholders to attain the overall development of the program.

Issues and Concerns

Issues and Concerns	School Head		Teachers	
	WM	VD	WM	VD
1. Increase workload	3	MA	3.82	A
2. Create Frustration and slow	3	MA	3.62	A
3. Devote less time to other aspects	3	MA	4.1	A
4. Create tension in the school	1	D	3.43	A
5. Increased staff involvement in decision making	2	SA	3.2	MA
6. Policies are not clearly cleared	2	SA	3.8	MA
7. Lack of community Participation	2	SA	4.4	SA
8. Lack of training and workshops relating to SBM.	3	MA	4.32	SA
9. Lack of fund resources on the implementation.	3	MA	4.54	SA
10. Lack of motivation from the implementer.	3	MA	4.21	SA
GRAND MEAN	2.5	MA	3.9	A

Table 1 shows the lists of issues and concerns relating to the implementation of school based management program. Item 1,2,3,8,9 and 10 refers to Increase workload, create frustration and slow, devote less time to other aspects, lack of training and workshops relating to SBM, lack of fund resources on the implementation, and lack of motivation from the implementer got the highest weighted mean of 3, which verbally described as moderately agree and consider as the most concerns of the principals and create tension was marked as the least concerns. This implies that principal perceived the program add them additional burden in terms managing their task from one task to another. It can be noticed also that lack of motivation from the implementer was also their concerns. This implies that after the implementation, there's no additional feedback on what's the next process or is there any additional training for the awareness of the stakeholders. Teachers on the other hand, item 9 which refers to "lack of fund resources on the implementation" got the highest weighted mean of 4.54 which verbally described as strongly agree as their most topmost concerns. This implies that teachers perceived that there is not enough resource for the implementation of the program and this might affect the overall outcome. Then it was followed by lack of community participation, lack of motivation from the implementer, devote less time to other aspects and item 5 refers to "Increased staff involvement in decision making" got the least perceived issues of the teachers. This implies that teachers involvement on the development of the program was encourage. Therefore, their time and task were increased and this led to another task and burden on them. This is that when teachers given additional task, they might be no longer prepared and focus on their teaching task.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Based from the results of the study, the researcher concludes that the level of participation of internal and external stakeholders in school based management program was still in the process of knowing what are the process and steps in achieving the overall mission of the program. In addition, principal and the teachers were bombarded with additional task and this affect their limited time at school and teaching duties. Moreover, lack of financial resources was also the problem on the implementation. Hence, the researcher believed that there are more things to improved before we can attain the mission of this program.

It is recommended that the proposed action plan be adopted by the proper authorities to address the identified areas of concerns and problems. This research study might be deliberated by the public officials, school heads, teachers, parents and different stakeholders so that they will be encouraged to continuously support the schools operation for the benefit of all the stakeholders, most especially to the learners.

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